

ISic3420

I.Sicily inscription 3420

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

limestone (?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Theatre, in the scaenae frons

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Teatro Romano di
Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644815

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. La cultura epigrafica della colonia di Catina nell'alto impero. In Salmeri, G., Raggi, A., Baroni, A.(eds.), *Colonie romane nel mondo greco*. Rome. pp. 233-254. At 241

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